

MICROSTRUCTURAL CHARACTERISATION OF COPPER/CARBON NANOFIBRE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The thermal conductivity and microstructure of a CuTi-0.5/CNF composite has been investigated. Microstructural characterisation involved FIB milling coupled with SEM microscopy, to obtain fibre distribution, and TEM microscopy, to study the fibre/matrix interface. From this, predictions of $\kappa_{\text{composite}}$ were made and compared to measured values.

Keywords: Metal matrix composite, thermal conductivity, carbon nanofibre, focussed ion beam tomography, transmission electron microscopy.

INTRODUCTION

Materials with high thermal conductivities, κ , are required for use as heat distributors in high heat flux applications [1]. There has been considerable interest in copper/carbon nanofibre and copper/carbon nanotube composites [2,3], whereby the high electronic thermal conductivity of copper ($400 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [1] is enhanced by the even higher phonon thermal conductivity of carbon nanofibres ($1200 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [4] and carbon nanotubes ($2980 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [5]. It is expected that these copper composites would exhibit similar enhancements as previously shown in aluminium composites reinforced with graphite nanofibres (GNFs) [6], $\kappa_{\text{Al/GNF}} = 285 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ with a loading of 3 wt%, and vapour grown carbon fibres (VGCFs) [7], $\kappa_{\text{Al/VGCF}} = 642 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ with a loading of 36.5 vol%.

To achieve high thermal conductivities, the fibre reinforcements must maintain their graphitic structure and be well-bonded to the matrix. Unfortunately, copper does not wet carbon, (wetting angle = 120°) [8]. Lower wetting angles are achieved by the addition of carbide formers, such as titanium, chromium and vanadium [8]. An in-depth study of the composite microstructure is therefore required to understand the effect of these additives on the effective composite thermal conductivity, $\kappa_{\text{composite}}$. In this work, Cu/CNF composites containing 5 wt% titanium (CuTi-0.5/CNF) were studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Composite Fabrication

The CNFs used in this study were from Showa Denko (vapour grown CNF grade). CNFs were coated with Cu using an electroless deposition technique [9], to obtain a 20% fibre volume fraction. Ti nanoparticles (5 wt%), with diameters ranging from 100 – 200 nm, and Cu coated CNFs were mixed together. The composite was then consolidated by hot pressing the powder mixture at 900 °C under a pressure of 35 MPa for 2 hours in a high strength graphite die.

Microstructural Characterisation

Microstructural observations were carried out throughout the fabrication process, from the ‘as received’ fibre to the consolidated material.

The structure of the CNF was determined using x-ray diffraction (XRD) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). XRD patterns were obtained using a Phillips PW1820 diffractometer with a Cu K α target, operated at 40 kV and 40 mA, at 0.05° step size and 0.6° per minute scan speed. The X-ray beam was narrowed using 1/2° divergence and anti-scatter slits, and a 0.2 mm receiving slit. TEM micrographs of the CNF and composite material were obtained using a Phillips CM30. The Cu coated CNFs were studied in the scanning electron microscope (SEM), a JEOL 6340 FEGSEM.

The variation in CNF arrangement in the composite was determined using a focussed ion beam (FIB) milling workstation coupled with SEM imaging, using the FEI Helios-Nanolab. SEM micrographs were sequentially collected after ion milling away 120 nm thick sections. A total of 190 SEM micrographs were collected and a 25 x 25 x 22.8 μm^3 volume of material was studied.

The CNF/Cu interface was probed using electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) and elemental maps obtained by energy filtered TEM (EFTEM) was acquired in the FEI Technai F20 FEGTEM.

PREDICTING EFFECTIVE COMPOSITE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY

Predictions of the effective thermal conductivity of the composite were made using an effective medium approach [10]. Both the formulation and computation of the problem are based on simple algebraic functions, whereby the effects of inclusion volume fraction, shape, aspect ratio, anisotropy, orientation, non-straightness, interfacial thermal properties and size have been considered. More details of the model can be found in reference [11]. Comparisons were made between predicted and measured values, where measurements were made using the laser flash technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Carbon Nanofibre Structure

The CNFs have a nested tubular structure (Figure 1), whereby each tube is seamless and consists of rolled graphene sheet. There is no orientational relationship between the

graphene sheets in adjacent tubes, resulting in larger (002) d-spacings, 3.409 Å, compared to graphite, 3.367 Å [12]. The graphitic nature of the CNF is exhibited in both XRD (Figure 2) and TEM electron diffraction (insert in Figure 1), as sharp diffraction peaks and distinct diffraction spots. The XRD peaks were identified and used to calculate the CNF lattice parameters, $a = 2.46 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 6.788 \text{ \AA}$, which differs slightly from the ideal graphite structure ($a = 2.468 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 6.734 \text{ \AA}$).

Observations of the Cu coated CNFs (Figure 3), revealed good Cu coverage; though bare CNFs were observed. The lack of Cu coating on these areas could arise from either incomplete coating during the deposition process or spallation during handling. The copper grains formed by the electroless deposition technique were several 100 nm in diameter.

Figure 1: TEM micrograph and electron diffraction pattern (insert) of CNF. CNF has a nested tubular structure. Distinct spots arise from the (002) planes and the ring of spots result from the (100) planes.

Figure 2: XRD pattern, showing peaks arising from the (002), (100), (004) and (110) planes. The lattice parameters are $a = 2.46 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 6.788 \text{ \AA}$. The (100) peak is broadened by other carbon phases.

Figure 3: SEM micrograph of copper coated carbon nanofibre. Most of the fibres are coated, though a few exposed fibres are observed.

Composite Microstructure

Optical microscopy showed anisotropic fibre arrangement, where fibres were aligned in stratified layers in the pressing direction whilst in the in-plane direction, fibres were randomly oriented. This fibre arrangement is classified as 2D-random. Figure 4 shows the SEM micrograph of the composite after ion milling. The CNF are not homogeneously dispersed within the Cu matrix and tends to form agglomerates, ranging from 5 – 25 μm in diameter. These large agglomerates tend to contain voids, as the electrolyte cannot penetrate into the centre during the Cu deposition process. Voids are also observed between the CNF/Cu interface and within the Cu matrix, an indication that full densification was not achieved during consolidation.

An intermediate phase, titanium carbide (TiC), was observed around some of the CNFs. The Ti diffused to and reacted with the CNF surface. In some cases, whole CNFs were converted into TiC. This interlayer was expected at the CNF/Cu interfaces, as the diffusion distance estimated from the diffusivity of Ti in Cu under the hot pressing conditions (30 μm) exceeds that of the average inter-fibre distance. Not all the Ti reacted to form TiC, as clusters of unreacted Ti were observed.

Figure 4: SEM micrograph of CuTi-0.5/CNF composite. Surface was prepared by ion milling. Fibre agglomerates, voids and interaction layers are observed. The horizontal features are artefacts of the milling process and are known as curtaining.

The through thickness composite microstructure was not homogeneous (Figure 5). Large changes were observed as slices were progressively milled away. Variations in fibre density were observed within the volume studied, such as agglomerates 9.6 μm thick (from slice 31 – 111) and the micrograph of Slice 111 shows the fibres to be well dispersed and evenly distributed. This shows that it is necessary to check for any variations in fibre arrangement throughout the composite. It was not possible to obtain a 3D reconstruction of the composite from the milled slices, due to the lack of information as images were acquired at slice thicknesses comparable to that of the CNF diameter.

The TiC interlayer was studied in greater detail by TEM microscopy. Figure 6 shows the degradation of the CNF graphitic structure, where 50 nm of the CNF surface was

amorphous, whilst the centre remained crystalline. The formation of amorphous carbon is detrimental to its thermal conductivity, making it lower than expected. EFTEM elemental mapping confirmed that the interlayer formed between the Cu matrix and CNF and was Ti-rich, with thicknesses ranging from several nms to a few μms . Quantitative EELS spectra analysis, determined the composition to be $\text{TiC}_{0.94}$. The Ti was observed to penetrate 33 nm ahead of the $\text{CNF}/\text{TiC}_{0.94}$ interface, which caused the disruption of the CNF structure and the formation of amorphous carbon.

The $\text{TiC}_{0.94}$ acted as a thermal barrier, quantified by the interface thermal resistance, R_{bd} . The effective R_{bd} of the $\text{TiC}_{0.94}$ interlayer calculated by dividing the interlayer thickness (100 nm) by its κ ($5.65 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) was $1.77 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. Cu-Ti phases were also identified within the Cu matrix.

Figure 5: Series of SEM micrographs taken after consecutive ion milling of 120 nm thick slices. Micrographs are displayed with slice intervals of 10, a distance of 1.2 μm . Micrograph width corresponds to 25 μm .

Figure 6: TEM micrograph of carbon nanofibre embedded in the matrix. Observe the presence of a reaction layer, a region where the carbon is amorphous and a region where the CNF retains its graphitic structure. The amorphous carbon layer is 50 nm thick.

Figure 7: EFTEM mapping of carbon, copper and titanium in a region surrounding a single CNF. Observe two Ti rich areas, at the CNF/Cu interface (TiC) and within the matrix (Cu-Ti alloy).

Cracks were observed at the CNF/TiC_{0.94} interface. These cracks further limit heat transport, as the CNF has a reduced area in contact with the surrounding matrix. Cracking occurs as a result of differences in the CTE and molar volumes of the Cu, TiC_{0.94} and CNF phases.

Predicted Effective Composite Thermal Conductivity

The measured thermal conductivity of the composite was $200 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. All predictions assumed an inclusion volume fraction of 20%, that the inclusions are prolate spheroids with an aspect ratio of 50 and $\kappa_{\text{matrix}} = 400 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. Initial predictions were made for aligned isotropic fibres, where $\kappa_{\text{fibre(isotropic)}} = 1200 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and later modified to include a 2-D random fibre arrangement. The κ_{CNF} was expected to be different along the length of the fibre, $\kappa_{\text{CNF,||}}$, and perpendicular to the fibre axis, $\kappa_{\text{CNF,\perp}}$, similar to the anisotropy observed in graphite. $\kappa_{\text{CNF,||}}$ and $\kappa_{\text{CNF,\perp}}$ were assumed to be 1200 and $30 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, respectively. The presence of the TiC_{0.94} interlayer was also accounted for by using $R_{\text{bd}} = 1.77 \times 10^{-8}$. The predicted values are summarised in Table 1.

Going from an aligned to 2D random fibre arrangement, followed by isotropic to anisotropic fibre κ , showed a progressive decrease in $\kappa_{\text{composite}}$, though the predicted values remained larger than those measured. Introduction of R_{bd} reduced $\kappa_{\text{composite}}$ further. The measured κ was observed to be worse than that predicted with voids as the inclusion. It is possible that the CNF have no better benefit compared to voids, as cracking was observed at the CNF/TiC_{0.94} interface and the loss of fibre crystallinity. The reduction in $\kappa_{\text{composite}}$ to the measured value is achieved when $\kappa_{\text{matrix}} = 275 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, indicating that κ_{matrix} is reduced by alloying with Ti.

Table 1: Summary of predicted κ_{comp}

κ_{comp} /W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	Isotropic CNF		Anisotropic CNF		Voids
	aligned	2D random	$R_{\text{bd}} = 0$ W m ⁻² K ⁻¹	$R_{\text{bd}} = 1.77 \times 10^{-8}$ W m ⁻² K ⁻¹	
Transverse	489	489	282	281	266
In-plane	560	526	410	405	290

CONCLUSIONS

In depth study of the composite microstructure, elucidated the reasons for the low measured thermal conductivity of the CuTi-0.5/CNF composite. The main reasons were the decoupling of the carbon nanofibre from the surrounding matrix material as a result of cracking, the loss of fibre crystallinity which reduces the carbon nanofibre thermal conductivity and the reduction of matrix thermal conductivity due to alloying with excess titanium.

As expected, the titanium additive formed an interfacial carbide layer between the copper and carbon nanofibre phases. Unfortunately, weak bonding between the carbide and carbon nanofibre resulted in cracking at that interface and excess titanium detrimentally reduced both the fibre crystallinity and matrix thermal conductivity.

Results from this work indicate that a high thermal conductivity copper/carbon nanofibre composite can be obtained by reducing the negative effects of titanium mentioned above. The additive materials and processing conditions need to be chosen, so as to limit the extent of the carbide reaction in order to minimise the formation of amorphous carbon at the carbon nanofibre surface. An optimum additive concentration which does not drastically reduce the matrix thermal conductivity, also needs to be determined.

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